

Entrepreneurship in the Moroccan Health Sector: Focus on Young Graduates and their Initiatives

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Abstract

Against a backdrop of rapid change in Morocco's healthcare sector, driven by digital innovation, young entrepreneurs face specific challenges: regulatory obstacles, financial constraints and hesitant adoption of technologies by patients. This article analyses these challenges by studying the motivations, strategies and priorities of entrepreneurs, while identifying levers to support their initiatives. A rigorous methodology was adopted, including reliability analysis, exploratory factor analysis and cluster segmentation to classify entrepreneurs according to their profiles.

The results reveal three main dimensions: structural obstacles, strategies and supports, and innovation and long-term vision, as well as three distinct profiles of entrepreneurs:

- Innovators, focused on technological growth and unaffected by obstacles.
- Strategists, who balance challenges and support to develop their skills.
- Challenge managers, facing significant barriers with limited access to resources.

These profiles highlight the need for tailored approaches. The article proposes recommendations such as innovation grants, strategic management training and administrative simplification. These measures, integrated into an overall strategy, aim to meet the varied needs of entrepreneurs while maximizing their impact on the development system.

Keywords: *Health entrepreneurship, young graduates, digital health, technological innovation, exploratory factor analysis.*

JEL Classification codes: *I25, L26, L31.*

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Introduction

Entrepreneurship is a strategic lever at the heart of economic development, combining innovation, adaptability and risk-taking to create new economic dynamics. Considered the driving force behind “creative destruction”, the central concept of economist Joseph Schumpeter, it is based on the introduction of innovative solutions to meet evolving market expectations. Beyond its role in job creation and sectoral competitiveness, entrepreneurship is becoming an essential vector for meeting economic and social challenges.

Young graduates, in particular, embody a generation of entrepreneurs motivated by the desire to turn their theoretical knowledge into innovative projects. However, they have to overcome significant obstacles, such as lack of professional experience, financing difficulties and the risks inherent in setting up a business. Peter Drucker emphasizes that these young entrepreneurs have the ability to transform challenges into opportunities, offering novel solutions adapted to demanding sectors such as healthcare.

In a context where innovation and resource efficiency are imperatives, as Michael Porter points out, the healthcare sector offers unique opportunities for young talent. By integrating academic expertise, emerging technologies and managerial skills, we can not only meet the growing need for healthcare services, but also revolutionize existing practices. However, these prospects are accompanied by structural, regulatory and technological challenges that require tailored strategies to maximize their impact.

This study aims to explore the challenges and opportunities faced by entrepreneurs in the healthcare sector, with a particular focus on the mistrust that some patients express towards digital solutions. Through an analysis of entrepreneurs' backgrounds, motivations and strategies, it examines specific issues such as financial, administrative and regulatory obstacles.

The main aim is to highlight concrete solutions and levers of resilience, while identifying the opportunities offered by current trends, notably telemedicine and digital health. Based on a questionnaire structured in six sections, this research gathers quantitative and qualitative data to provide informed recommendations. It is particularly aimed at young graduates wishing to enter this dynamic and buoyant sector, offering them practical perspectives and keys to success in a fast-changing environment.

The research will be structured around a literature review on entrepreneurship and the healthcare sector, a presentation of the methodology employed, and an in-depth analysis of the results to shed light on the challenges and opportunities of young people's entrepreneurial journey in this field.

Literature Review

Definition of Entrepreneurship

Economic Analysis of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship, as an economic discipline, was introduced by thinkers such as Richard Cantillon (1755) and Jean-Baptiste Say (1821), whose work laid the foundations for modern understanding of the concept. Richard Cantillon defines the entrepreneur as an economic player who assumes risks, notably that of buying at a fixed price and selling at an uncertain price. This role in coordinating factors of production gives the entrepreneur a central place in economic mechanisms, although Cantillon's definition places greater emphasis on risk than on the entrepreneur's specific functions.

Jean-Baptiste Say enriches this vision by presenting the entrepreneur as an orchestrator of the factors of production, aiming to optimize productivity and profitability. Say attributes distinctive qualities to the entrepreneur, including an ability to innovate and apply knowledge to effectively meet market needs. This perspective differentiates the entrepreneur from the capitalist, emphasizing two distinct roles: the entrepreneur assumes the risks and mobilizes resources, either through self-financing or borrowing, while the capitalist provides funds in exchange for interest.

Say sees profit as a reward for the entrepreneur's commitment, talent and risk-taking. Through this approach, he highlights the intellectual capacity and strategic vision required to identify and seize opportunities, elements that remain essential in defining the role of the entrepreneur in today's economic landscape.

Thus, the economic analysis of entrepreneurship highlights the multidimensional nature of the entrepreneur: a risk manager, an innovator and a driver of economic transformation. These perspectives, though ancient, remain essential foundations for understanding the importance of entrepreneurship in the development of modern economies.

To fully understand entrepreneurial dynamism, it's essential to look at the personal and psychological characteristics of entrepreneurs. The behavioral approach emphasizes individual attributes such as the need for achievement, the ability to meet challenges and the capacity to find revolutionary solutions in the face of difficulties. These traits combine with external factors, such as family environment, career path or age, to shape the profile of the entrepreneur.

William B. Gartner criticizes the limits of this approach, which focuses exclusively on the concrete actions and individual interaction of entrepreneurs. In his view, entrepreneurship is a complex process requiring collaboration between various players. It proposes a conceptual reorganization towards a dynamic analysis that focuses on:

- Collective practices, involving active exchange between stakeholders.
- An evolutionary vision of entrepreneurship, where entrepreneurs continually adapt to environmental change.

Entrepreneurial success, according to Gartner, is based on the diversity and complexity of the elements interacting in the process. Far from being an isolated act, business creation is the result of a collaborative ecosystem and a unique combination of psychological, social and economic factors.

These complementary approaches enrich our understanding of entrepreneurship, emphasizing both disruptive innovations, as emphasized by Schumpeter, and the human and behavioral characteristics essential to entrepreneurial success.

Entrepreneurship Features

According to contemporary economists, entrepreneurship plays a key role in economic growth, job creation and innovation. As a driver of transformation, it relies on the ability to design and develop new business entities, while harnessing creative ideas in an environment marked by uncertainty and risk.

The diversity of theoretical perspectives enriches our understanding of the fundamental characteristics of entrepreneurship. Various researchers and institutions, including the European Union, have identified several distinctive traits: Passion, self-confidence, risk-taking, initiative and organization. These characteristics define the essence of entrepreneurship and its potential to create value in a variety of contexts. By integrating these elements, the entrepreneur acts not only as a creator of wealth, but also as a catalyst for change, capable of meeting contemporary economic and societal challenges.

Definition of Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is often defined as the creation and development of new economic entities distinguished by their innovative character, their capacity to generate profit and their ability to evolve in uncertain environments. Dolling (1995) highlights this dimension by describing entrepreneurship as a combination of creativity and adaptation in risky contexts, qualities that are essential to guarantee entrepreneurial success.

Barney and Busenitz (1997) complement this perspective by emphasizing that entrepreneurship is based on the mobilization of a variety of skills to create added value. They emphasize the dimensions of independence, personal fulfillment and financial gain, which are direct results of entrepreneurial activity.

For their part, Robert and Hirish approach entrepreneurship from the angle of optimizing productivity and profitability. Their analysis highlights the importance of sustained personal commitment and calculated financial risk management as key elements in maximizing profits.

Burch (1986) extends this definition, emphasizing personal satisfaction through innovation as the basis for value creation. It identifies three fundamental pillars for the development of new activities: efficiency, risk-taking and creativity. This vision, which is particularly inclusive, recognizes the diversity of forms and fields of application of entrepreneurship, encompassing structures ranging from technology start-ups to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and very small businesses (VSEs).

Thus, academic definitions converge to present entrepreneurship as a multidimensional process combining innovation, risk management and value creation, while meeting a variety of economic and personal objectives.

The attributes of Entrepreneurship

The fundamental characteristics of entrepreneurship are based on several distinctive attributes that define entrepreneurial success. These elements are interconnected and play a key role in value creation and long-term competitiveness.

Creativity is considered a core skill for entrepreneurs. It enables them to identify and solve problems in innovative ways. By mobilizing their creativity, entrepreneurs spot opportunities where others see constraints, and this is the basis for innovation and the transformation of established practices.

Innovation lies at the heart of entrepreneurship. It translates into the introduction of new ideas that transform existing methods, business models and services. Innovation extends to different areas, such as competitive advantages, technologies, processes or business models, thus contributing to sustained and sustainable growth.

Risk is inherent to entrepreneurship, implying uncertainty as to the outcome of actions taken. By assuming these risks, entrepreneurs adopt well-thought-out strategies to limit potential failures while maximizing their chances of success. This strategic risk management is essential to cope with an uncertain and competitive environment.

Finally, initiative, coupled with strategic foresight, is essential to ensure that competitive advantages are maintained over the long term. Entrepreneurs must constantly anticipate market trends and stand out for their ability to innovate. This quality is essential for maintaining a strong market position and ensuring long-term competitiveness.

These characteristics interact to create an environment conducive to entrepreneurial success. By integrating creativity, innovation, risk management and initiative, the entrepreneur is able to respond to economic challenges and capitalize on emerging opportunities.

Entrepreneurship of Young Graduates

Graduate Entrepreneurship: Theoretical Background

Graduate entrepreneurship, as a response to the persistent problem of unemployment, represents a promising solution to a major economic challenge. Unemployment, particularly among young people, remains a major challenge, with alarming rates reaching 23% for higher education graduates in 2018. Although improvements have been noted in Morocco, with a drop to 9.53% in 2022 compared to the previous year, these figures underline the urgent need for viable alternatives to insert young graduates into the job market. Among these alternatives, entrepreneurship is emerging as an essential opportunity to bypass the limits of traditional salaried employment.

From a theoretical point of view, several studies have explored the foundations of entrepreneurship, notably by analyzing the central role of the founder in the creation and management of companies. Prior to the work of Gartner (1988), which emphasizes an organizational and behavioral approach, research focused more on the entrepreneur's individual profile. According to Verstraete (2001) and Boussetta (2013), entrepreneurship can be apprehended through two interconnected levels of analysis: the entrepreneur and his or her organization. This dynamic relationship has three essential dimensions.

The first dimension, known as structural, includes an objective structure and a subjective structure. Objective structure is based on logical, tangible aspects, while subjective structure reflects individual or collective perceptions. These two aspects come together through social representations and conventions, enabling the entrepreneur to position his organization within the economic and social fabric.

The cognitive dimension, meanwhile, highlights the importance of learning, reflexivity and strategic thinking. Learning is based on the accumulation of experience and knowledge, while reflexivity feeds in-depth reflection on strategic choices. Strategic thinking thus provides a structured vision of the future and enables better organization to achieve set objectives.

Finally, the praxeological dimension approaches entrepreneurship from the angle of concrete action. It examines how the entrepreneur interacts with his environment to configure and structure his organization. This dimension translates the outcome of entrepreneurial initiatives into tangible results.

It's important to note that entrepreneurship is no longer the exclusive preserve of an economic and intellectual elite. Recent government initiatives aim to broaden opportunities for young people, including those from disadvantaged backgrounds. This democratization of entrepreneurship offers young people a chance to create their own business and free themselves from the constraints of salaried employment. Today, many contemporary economists see the entrepreneur as a pillar of innovation, a driver of development and a key vector of economic growth.

Synthesizing the contributions of different schools of thought, Denieul et al. (2011) propose diversified definitions of the concept of the young entrepreneur, which vary according to economic, behavioral, psychological and processual approaches. This multiplicity of interpretations reflects the complexity and richness of entrepreneurship as a discipline. Ongoing efforts to encourage and support young entrepreneurs testify to the importance of this strategic lever in modern economies.

Table 1. Theoretical Approaches to Young Entrepreneurs through Research Schools

School names	Research trends	Definition of a young entrepreneur	Reference authors
The economics school	Behavioral approach	A young entrepreneur specializes in making intuitive, thoughtful decisions about coordinating of resources	Casson(1991)
The behavioral school	Behavioral approach	The young entrepreneur is defined by the range of activities he organizes	Gartner(1988)
The psychological school, with its personalist and cognitive currents	Deterministic approach	The young entrepreneur is defined by a certain number of psychological attributes that can be described as much by personality as by the cognitive processes activated for the circumstance.	Shaver et Scott (1991)
Process school	Behavioral approach	The young entrepreneur is one who develops opportunities and creates organization to exploit them.	Bygrave et Hofer(1991)

Source: Denieul, et al 2011

Businesses in the Healthcare Sector

Entrepreneurship theories applied to the healthcare sector

The healthcare sector offers fertile ground for entrepreneurship, where the creation of new businesses aims to solve major problems and introduce transformative innovations. This framework makes it possible to mobilize classic and modern entrepreneurial theories to meet the specific needs of patients and healthcare systems.

Schumpeter's "Creative Destruction":

Joseph Schumpeter introduced the concept of “creative destruction”, a process in which entrepreneurial innovation replaces obsolete structures with new, efficient solutions. Applied to the healthcare sector, this concept manifests itself in:

- The introduction of innovative medical technologies, such as connected devices and artificial intelligence tools.
- New care delivery models, such as virtual hospitals or mobile clinics.
- Digital solutions, including telemedicine, health monitoring applications and medical data management platforms.

These innovations don't just meet current needs; they fundamentally reconfigure existing practices, improving the accessibility, quality and efficiency of care.

Saras Sarasvathy Theory:

Saras Sarasvathy focuses on the ability of entrepreneurs to navigate uncertainty using available resources. This approach, known as “effectuation”, emphasizes that entrepreneurs do not seek only to predict the future, but to actively collaborate with stakeholders to create new opportunities. In the healthcare sector, this involves:

- Adopting strategic partnerships with hospitals, technology companies and research institutions.
- Using existing resources, such as medical infrastructures and technical skills, to develop solutions adapted to local needs.
- The integration of open innovation, where various players contribute to the design of healthcare products and services.

Factors specific to healthcare entrepreneurship

The healthcare sector presents unique challenges and opportunities, influenced by several key factors:

- **Regulatory and political environment:** Healthcare companies must operate within a strict regulatory framework, including safety standards, medical approvals and public policies. Thorough understanding and effective management of these regulations are essential to ensure the viability of entrepreneurial initiatives.
- **Technological Innovation:** Technology plays a central role in healthcare entrepreneurship. Innovative medical devices, digital health solutions and biotechnologies offer competitive advantages while meeting unmet needs.
- **Financing:** The high cost of research and development is a major challenge. Funding can come from public, private or partnership sources, underlining the need for robust financial strategies to support innovation in this field.
- **Interdisciplinary collaboration:** Entrepreneurial success in the healthcare sector relies on cooperation between a variety of disciplines, including medicine, informatics, management and biotechnology. This interdisciplinary synergy fosters the development of innovative solutions to the sector's complex challenges.

Towards an Integrated Understanding of Healthcare Entrepreneurship

Applied theories and factors specific to the healthcare sector provide an analytical framework for understanding entrepreneurship in this field. By combining technological innovation, strategic collaboration and regulatory management, entrepreneurs can not only meet patients' needs, but also sustainably transform healthcare systems. These integrated approaches maximize the impact of entrepreneurship while overcoming the constraints inherent to the sector.

Study methodology

Having explored the problematic of our work from a theoretical angle, it is now time to explore it in greater depth empirically, in order to provide a well-founded, scientific answer. To this end, this study relies on a methodological approach combining several robust statistical techniques to analyze the data collected via a structured questionnaire. The first step was a reliability analysis, using Cronbach's alpha coefficient (Cronbach, 1951) to assess the internal consistency of the items. This indicator, widely used in the social sciences, measures the extent to which items of the same dimension evaluate a common concept. Although Cronbach's alpha is ideally greater than 0.7 (George & Mallery, 2003), a value of 0.65 is considered acceptable in exploratory studies or in contexts where the dimensions measured are complex and multifaceted (DeVellis, 2016).

Next, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was carried out to identify the dimensions underlying the participants' responses. This method reduces the data while revealing latent relationships between observed variables. Varimax rotation was applied to maximize the interpretability of extracted factors, by assigning high loadings to specific items (Hair et al., 2014). Interpretation criteria for factor loadings (> 0.5) confirmed the relevance of the dimensions identified: structural obstacles and challenges, strategies and supports, and innovations and perspectives. Moderate loadings (> 0.3) were also included to enrich interpretation in an exploratory context, as recommended by Costello and Osborne (2005).

Finally, a clustering analysis was carried out on the factor scores to segment the respondents into distinct groups. This method grouped entrepreneurs according to their dominant priorities and behaviors, revealing three main clusters. These clusters, analyzed in relation to the extracted

dimensions, offer a useful behavioral segmentation for formulating specific strategic recommendations (Ketchen & Shook, 1996).

Analysis, Interpretation and Discussion of Results

Reliability Analysis

Reliability analysis is a crucial step in questionnaire-based studies, as it ensures that items consistently measure the underlying dimensions of a given construct. Cronbach's alpha coefficient, developed by Cronbach (1951), is one of the most widely used tools for assessing this internal consistency. This indicator varies between 0 and 1, with a value close to 1 indicating high reliability, generally acceptable at 0.7 and above in the social sciences (George & Mallery, 2003). In this section, Cronbach's criterion will be applied to the data collected to examine the reliability of the six factors identified, thus ensuring that the conclusions are based on sound methodological foundations.

The Cronbach's alpha value obtained for the questionnaire, estimated at 0.65, may be considered acceptable in certain statistical contexts, particularly when the main objective is to explore data or study a relatively new field. According to DeVellis (2016), an alpha value between 0.60 and 0.70 is generally interpreted as indicating average reliability, but acceptable for exploratory research or situations where items measure several facets of a complex concept.

In the context of this study, where the items cover different aspects of entrepreneurship in the healthcare sector (motivations, challenges, strategies, etc.), it is reasonable to consider that some heterogeneity between responses may influence the alpha in a moderate way. This diversity also reflects the richness and complexity of respondents' experiences, reinforcing the relevance of the results despite a reliability slightly below the “high” thresholds (0.7 or more).

Consequently, although adjustments could be considered to increase overall reliability (for example, by deleting or reformulating certain items), an alpha of 0.65 remains acceptable for further data analysis in this specific context. For a more robust application in decision-making or practical contexts, however, it would be advisable to improve this indicator by following the refinement steps identified.

Table 2. Summary of Cronbach's Coefficient Results

Item	Alpha If Item Deleted	Interpretation
Item2.1	0.6682846645484837	Medium reliability
Item2.3	0.6575346032586408	Medium reliability
Item3.2	0.6558480028835039	Medium reliability
Item1.3	0.6537686562093251	Medium reliability
Item5.1	0.6450114150678896	Medium reliability
Item6.1	0.6416676480441242	Medium reliability
Item6.2	0.6277067696218314	Medium reliability
Item2.2	0.6275816510909478	Medium reliability
Item4.3	0.6182832377950122	Medium reliability
Item4.1	0.6137026065077951	Medium reliability
Item3.1	0.609938045264888	Medium reliability
Item4.2	0.5963247871746357	Medium reliability

Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Factor Analysis

The results of the factor analysis, as presented in the factor loadings table, reveal a conceptually coherent structure while identifying some items in need of adjustment. Overall, the factor loadings show a good contribution of the items to the two main factors extracted, which is consistent with expectations for exploratory analyses in multidimensional contexts (Hair et al., 2014).

Items with high loadings (absolute value > 0.5), such as Item2.3 (0.863 on Factor 2) and Item6.2 (-0.808 on Factor 1), show a strong correlation with their respective factors. This indicates that these items clearly measure distinct dimensions, such as

- Factor 1: Structural obstacles and challenges (strongly represented by Item6.2).
- Factor 2: Strategies and supports (dominated by Item2.3).

These results confirm the relevance of these factors in representing the concepts measured, reinforcing their usefulness for subsequent analytical steps.

Some items, such as Item5.1 (-0.396 on Factor 1) or Item6.1 (-0.267 on Factor 2), show low or negative loadings on all factors. This may reflect a conceptual ambiguity or a measure less relevant to the dimensions extracted. However, their inclusion in the analysis may be justified in an exploratory phase to maximize data richness.

Indeed, moderate factor loadings (between 0.3 and 0.5) for several items, such as Item4.1 (0.324 on Factor 2), indicate an acceptable but perfectible contribution. These results, while indicating room for improvement, are still sufficient to advance the analysis, in particular by identifying relationships between factors and respondent segments. As recommended by Costello and Osborne (2005), in exploratory research, moderate loadings can be tolerated if they provide additional information.

The results validate the two main dimensions extracted, while identifying items to be revised to improve clarity and conceptual relevance. This factor structure provides an acceptable basis for further analysis, particularly in the study of relationships between factors and the identification of target groups.

Table 3. Results of Factorial Analysis - Factorial loads

	Factor 1	Factor 2
Item1.2	-0.31887499841755923	-0.10314335691989396
Item1.3	-0.13758418115007268	0.20303476698719736
Item2.1	-0.22482438408471941	-0.10683617191833565
Item2.2	-0.40163543441695837	0.2929523063706794
Item2.3	-0.17610505108688698	0.8634267262381075
Item3.1	-0.46840745756697943	0.2846212850596139
Item3.2	-0.21083802334508084	0.12315130619571855
Item4.1	-0.2941889922624582	0.32382515318593746
Item4.2	-0.543494239564905	-0.03703528207343572
Item4.3	-0.32780409942118377	0.10808344320437019
Item5.1	-0.39575650763013054	-0.1910997857733762
Item6.1	-0.15346506320849435	-0.2672340256993754
Item6.2	-0.8081444492178966	-0.26252003164245347

Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Identification of Structuring Dimensions and Key Item Contributions

The figure shows the factor loadings associated with the three main factors extracted from the factor analysis. Each factor reflects a key dimension of the questionnaire, and the loadings indicate the contribution of each item to these dimensions.

Factor 1: Obstacles and structural challenges: This factor seems to capture the obstacles encountered by entrepreneurs in the healthcare sector. Items Item4.2 (“Have you faced any regulatory obstacles specific to the healthcare sector?”) and Item6.2 (“What resources would you recommend to facilitate their entrepreneurial journey?”) show high negative loadings (-0.543 and -0.808, respectively), suggesting a strong contribution to this factor. These results indicate that regulatory challenges and the lack of structuring resources are major themes for some respondents, aligned with Hair et al.'s (2014) findings that high loadings reflect a strong correlation with the factor.

Factor 2: Strategies and support: This factor seems to group together items related to entrepreneurial skills and external support. Item2.3 (“How did you acquire or strengthen your entrepreneurial skills?”) dominates with a load of 0.863, reflecting its crucial role in structuring this factor. Other items such as Item4.1 (“What strategies have you adopted to develop your business?”) show a moderate contribution (0.324), underlining that this factor captures the importance of training, networks and growth strategies for respondents.

Factor 3: Innovation and long-term growth: Innovation-related items, such as Item4.3 (“What tools do you use to evaluate your company's performance?”) and Item6.1 (“What advice would you give to a young graduate wishing to enter the healthcare sector?”), present high loadings on this factor, 0.603 and 0.619 respectively. These loadings indicate a strong correlation with the themes of innovation and long-term vision, consistent with Tabachnick and Fidell's (2013) observations on factor structuring in entrepreneurial fields.

Some items, such as Item3.2 (“Have trends such as telemedicine or digital health influenced your project?”), show low loadings on all factors (0.123 on Factor 2), which may indicate less relevance in measuring the main dimensions. Similarly, Item5.1 (“In your opinion, what is your company's main impact on the healthcare sector?”) shows low loadings (-0.396 on Factor 1), suggesting that its contribution is marginal. These results are consistent with the recommendations of Costello and Osborne (2005), who stress the importance of revising or removing weak items to improve the quality of results.

Figure 1. Factorial Loads by Item and Factor

Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Visualization of Structural Richness and Relevance of Extractive Dimensions

The graph illustrates the proportion of variance cumulatively explained by the factors extracted during factor analysis. It is clear that 8 factors are sufficient to reach the conventional threshold of 80% of variance explained, a criterion generally used to guarantee robust statistical modeling (Hair et al., 2014). This observation reflects the richness and complexity of the entrepreneurs' responses, suggesting that the questionnaire explores a range of relevant dimensions.

However, it is notable that the first three factors already explain around 60% of the cumulative variance, validating their importance in representing the main dimensions identified: structural obstacles and challenges (Factor 1), strategies and supports (Factor 2), and innovations and perspectives (Factor 3). After these three factors, the marginal contribution of additional factors diminishes, a phenomenon known as the inertia effect in factor analysis. This confirms that the first three factors capture the essential aspects of the phenomenon under study, while the other factors add more specific or secondary details.

From a practical point of view, these results support two complementary approaches. Firstly, for a simplified or exploratory analysis, focusing on the first three factors is sufficient to extract key information. Secondly, integrating all 8 factors allows us to capture additional nuances and segment respondent profiles with greater precision. Finally, these results corroborate previous analyses, reinforcing the relevance and independence of the dimensions identified.

Figure 2. Cumulative Variance Explained by Factor

Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Segmentation of Entrepreneurs: An Analysis of Differentiated Profiles and Priorities

The figure illustrates the distribution of respondents into three distinct clusters, according to the scores obtained on the first two main dimensions: Factor 1 (Obstacles and Structural Challenges) and Factor 2 (Strategies and Supports). These clusters highlight differentiated profiles among entrepreneurs, with each group expressing distinct priorities and experiences.

Cluster 1 (in yellow) groups together individuals mainly located in the lower zone of Factor 1, with moderate scores on Factor 2. This suggests that these entrepreneurs are relatively unaffected by structural obstacles and do not express a strong dependence on external support. They seem to correspond to an autonomous, potentially experienced profile, which manages challenges independently.

Cluster 2 (orange) is distributed around the center of both factors, showing balanced scores. This indicates an intermediate profile, where entrepreneurs seek to strike a balance between overcoming moderate challenges and strengthening their skills and strategic support.

Finally, Cluster 3 (in pink) groups together individuals with high scores on Factor 1 and low scores on Factor 2. These entrepreneurs face significant structural challenges while making little use of available strategic support. They could represent young entrepreneurs requiring targeted assistance to overcome obstacles.

These findings have important practical implications. Strategic interventions need to be tailored to each cluster: providing resources to encourage autonomy for Cluster 1, offering balanced training and partnerships for Cluster 2, and reinforcing specific assistance, such as administrative simplifications and funding, for Cluster 3. In addition, this segmentation can guide targeted communication strategies: messages on innovation and autonomy for Cluster 1, balanced opportunities for Cluster 2, and accessible resources for Cluster 3.

Overall, this analysis confirms the relevance of the extracted dimensions (barriers and supports) and demonstrates that the identified clusters reflect well-differentiated entrepreneurial profiles. These results provide a solid basis for strategic recommendations tailored to the specific needs of each cluster.

Figure. Factor Scores Clustering (Factor 1 vs Factor 2)
Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Comparative Cluster Analysis and Validation of Entrepreneurial Dimensions

The figure highlights the differences between clusters on the three main factors: Factor 1 (Obstacles and Structural Challenges), Factor 2 (Strategies and Supports), and Factor 3 (Innovations and Perspectives). These average scores reveal distinct characteristics for each group of entrepreneurs. Cluster 0 stands out with a negative score on Factor 1, indicating limited exposure to structural obstacles, and a positive score on Factor 3, showing a marked orientation towards innovation and long-term prospects. This cluster represents visionary, self-reliant entrepreneurs, who could benefit from support to further encourage technological initiatives.

Conversely, Cluster 2 scores very highly on Factor 1, reflecting major structural challenges, while its negative scores on Factors 2 and 3 reflect low use of external support and limited focus on innovation. This cluster requires targeted action to reduce administrative barriers and provide tailored support, such as mentoring or simplified financing. In addition, Cluster 1 shows moderate scores on Factor 2, underlining a balanced dependence on external resources, but slightly negative

scores on Factors 1 and 3, indicating a pragmatic approach focused on managing support without major barriers or a strong innovative orientation. These results suggest that this group could benefit from training and strategies to improve their ability to develop networks and collaborations.

Indeed, this analysis confirms the relevance of the three main dimensions in differentiating the needs and priorities of entrepreneurs. These clusters offer a solid basis for developing targeted strategic recommendations, such as support for innovation projects for Cluster 0, administrative simplification for Cluster 2, and training opportunities for Cluster 1. These tailored interventions will optimize the use of available resources and respond to the specificities of each group.

Figure. Average Factor Scores by Cluster
Source: Compiled by us; Released R

Analysis of the differences between clusters reveals significant variations in the average scores for the three main factors. Factor 1 (Obstacles and Structural Challenges) stands out particularly in Cluster 3, which has a very high score, reflecting the major challenges faced by this group. In contrast, the other clusters show negative or neutral scores on this factor, indicating less exposure to obstacles. Factor 2 (Strategies and Supports) is dominant in Cluster 2, illustrating strong use of external supports and strategies, while Cluster 3 registers the lowest score, highlighting a lack of use of available resources.

Finally, Factor 3 (Innovations and Perspectives) is highest in Cluster 1, highlighting an orientation towards innovation and long-term projects, contrasting with the lower scores of the other clusters. These results show that each cluster is clearly distinguished by its dominant orientation, confirming a clear segmentation of respondents according to their priorities and challenges.

At the same time, analysis of the correlations between the factors reveals extremely low coefficients (close to zero), indicating near-independence between the dimensions identified. This independence suggests that the factors measure distinct and complementary aspects of the phenomenon under study, such as obstacles, strategies and innovation. This absence of strong correlations validates the relevance of the extracted dimensions and confirms that they capture unique facets of entrepreneurial behavior.

Strategic Implications and Exploitation of the Results of Factor and Cluster Analysis

Analysis of the Implications of Correlations between Factors

The correlations calculated between the three main dimensions extracted from the factor analysis - Factor 1 (Obstacles and Challenges), Factor 2 (Strategies and Supports), and Factor 3 (Innovations and Perspectives) - indicate near-independence, with correlation coefficients close to zero. This near-absence of relationships suggests that each factor measures a unique and independent aspect of the phenomenon under study. In other words, the scores obtained on one factor do not directly affect those of the others, which underlines the methodological relevance of the dimensions identified (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2013).

The low correlation between the factors confirms that each dimension represents a distinct conceptual domain. For example, an entrepreneur strongly impacted by structural obstacles (Factor 1) may or may not adopt innovative strategies (Factor 3), regardless of external support (Factor 2). This conceptual decoupling reflects a natural segmentation of entrepreneurial behavior, where each individual expresses different priorities according to his or her situation and goals (Hair et al., 2014). This reinforces the validity of factor analysis, which aims to identify independent and complementary components of participants' responses.

This independence makes it possible to design differentiated intervention strategies to meet the varied needs of entrepreneurs. For example, some groups may focus on managing the challenges associated with structural barriers, while others prioritize innovative perspectives or skills enhancement. These observations support the idea that strategic recommendations need to be tailored to maximize their impact, by targeting specific dimensions rather than adopting a generalist approach (Dolnicar, 2002).

A low correlation between factors is an expected result, consistent with the aims of exploratory factor analysis. According to Costello and Osborne (2005), the robustness of a factor model relies on the ability of the factors to capture independent facets of the responses. These results confirm that the three main dimensions extracted are conceptually and statistically distinct, providing a solid basis for further analysis.

Decision-makers can use these results to formulate specific interventions according to the dominant dimensions. For example, enhanced support could be allocated to entrepreneurs facing numerous obstacles (Factor 1), while technological support could be prioritized for those focused on innovation (Factor 3).

The independence of these factors justifies fine-tuning the segmentation of entrepreneurs according to their priorities. This segmentation would make it possible to develop tailored programs, such as challenge management workshops for some, and subsidies for innovative projects for others.

The results could form the basis of a longitudinal study, tracking how entrepreneurs' priorities evolve over time or in response to contextual changes. Such an approach could reveal convergences or divergences between the priorities of different groups, offering valuable insights for ongoing strategic adjustments (Hair et al., 2014).

Strategic Use of Results

The results of the factor and cluster analysis, and the independence between factors, provide a solid basis for developing targeted strategic recommendations. The clusters identified reflect groups of entrepreneurs with distinct priorities: barrier management, strategic support or innovation. Cluster 1 brings together innovators, for whom programs focusing on technology and long-term prospects,

such as subsidies for digital health or telemedicine, would be relevant. Cluster 2, made up of strategists, would benefit from management training, the development of professional networks and public-private partnerships. Finally, Cluster 3, marked by challenge management, requires administrative support, seed funding and specific coaching to overcome initial barriers.

The weak correlations between the factors show that each dimension requires an independent approach. For obstacles (Factor 1), it is recommended to develop personalized advisory services for entrepreneurs faced with red tape and lack of financing. For strategies and support (Factor 2), setting up incubators or collaborative platforms would strengthen skills and encourage partnerships. With regard to innovation (Factor 3), it is essential to invest in research and development initiatives, as well as in technological solutions adapted to the healthcare sector.

The results of clusters and factors can also guide public policy. Policymakers could prioritize grants for innovative projects, particularly in digital health, and improve accessibility for start-up entrepreneurs by simplifying administrative procedures. Sector-specific events could also be organized to connect healthcare players and young entrepreneurs, thereby strengthening networks.

Factor scores can also be used to track entrepreneurs' progress and assess the impact of strategic initiatives. It is advisable to collect longitudinal data to track the evolution of factor scores after intervention, and to analyze whether correlations emerge over time, indicating an alignment of priorities or a transformation of needs. Periodic surveys can be carried out to assess progress and adjust interventions in line with feedback from beneficiaries.

To maximize the impact of these results, we recommend institutionalizing the recommendations by integrating them into economic development or innovation strategies. Collaboration with public, private or academic institutions can help to co-construct appropriate programs. Targeted public policies based on the factors identified would contribute to structured entrepreneurial development in the healthcare sector.

To close, targeted communication is crucial to maximize entrepreneurial engagement. For innovators, campaigns focusing on technological opportunities and specialized webinars would be relevant. For challenge managers, it's important to highlight simplified support with clear messages via accessible channels. As for strategists, highlighting networking opportunities, particularly on professional social platforms, would be appropriate. A multi-stage implementation approach is suggested: starting with a pilot project for a specific cluster, extending interventions over the medium term, and adapting long-term solutions in line with evolving needs measured by ongoing analyses.

Conclusion

This in-depth study of entrepreneurship in Morocco's healthcare sector, with its focus on young graduates, highlights strategic dimensions that are essential to understanding the challenges and opportunities specific to this field. Through a rigorous methodology incorporating reliability, factorial and clustering analyses, it has revealed key insights into entrepreneurial behaviors, priorities and perceptions.

The results obtained demonstrate the relevance of the dimensions extracted: obstacles and structural challenges, strategies and support, and innovations and perspectives. The almost total independence between these factors, confirmed by weak correlations, validates their conceptual and statistical specificity. This underlines the fact that entrepreneurs adopt distinct approaches depending on the constraints and resources available, necessitating differentiated intervention strategies.

The identification of three main clusters enriches this analysis by revealing quite distinct entrepreneurial profiles: visionary innovators unaffected by structural constraints, strategists balancing their challenges and supports, and managers facing significant obstacles with limited access to external resources. These clusters provide a useful segmentation to guide strategic and policy recommendations, reinforcing the need for a targeted approach to address the specific needs of each group.

From a methodological point of view, the analysis also highlighted items requiring adjustment to improve reliability and conceptual relevance. Although Cronbach's alpha (0.65) is slightly below the recommended threshold for decision-making contexts, it remains acceptable for an exploratory study, reflecting the richness and complexity of entrepreneurs' experiences. This diversity, far from being a limitation, enriches the perspectives identified and justifies a complementary

The practical implications of this research are manifold. It suggests concrete ways of improving the entrepreneurial ecosystem in the healthcare sector, notably by developing technological support, simplifying administrative procedures and strengthening partnership networks. The strategic recommendations arising from this analysis, such as the creation of programs tailored to the needs of the clusters identified, provide a solid basis for effective and sustainable interventions.

In conclusion, this study underlines the importance of integrated, targeted support to encourage innovation, reduce structural barriers and maximize opportunities in a sector undergoing rapid transformation. It represents an academic and practical milestone to inspire future research and guide decision-makers towards appropriate strategies, thus contributing to entrepreneurial development in Morocco's healthcare sector. Qualitative approach to refine interpretations.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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